

Static tests on cruciform welded connections with imperfections

Effects of porosities, root gap, misalignment, and weld asymmetry

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ABSTRACT

Welding imperfections remain a significant concern in the fabrication of structures and components across diverse industries. Within the field of civil engineering, prEN 1993-1-8 requires an ISO 5817 quality level C for welded connections subjected to static loading. This requirement is far from common practice for certain steel structures, particularly those in EN 1090-2 execution class 1. However, the background justifications to ban quality level D are limited. An extensive experimental campaign has been performed on 21 specimens with different imperfections to study the impact of weld quality levels defined in ISO 5817 on the static resistance of welded connections. The tested specimens were load-carrying cruciform joints with imperfections such as root gap, porosities, linear misalignment and fillet weld asymmetry.

Non-destructive tests, including visual testing, 3D scanning, and ultrasonic testing, were employed to accurately identify the size and location of each imperfection. The findings revealed the distinct influence of each imperfection on the weld resistance, providing valuable insights that may be used to reassess the necessity for quality level C required by prEN 1993-1-8 for static resistance.

Keywords: Static resistance, weld imperfections, load-carrying cruciform joints.

1 INTRODUCTION

Welded connections are of paramount importance for maintaining structural integrity of constructions. However, the fabrication process may lead to imperfections even if validated procedures are applied. Various factors including exposure to environment, inadequate cleaning, material contamination, welding in poor conditions and poor fit-up, contribute to the occurrence of weld imperfections. To address these challenges and ensures the reliability of welded structures, a comprehensive framework of standards has been established to govern welding practices and mitigate the associated risks.

One notable standard, EN 1090-2 (1) outlines the requirements for executing steel structures, categorizing them into four distinct execution classes denoted as “EXC”. These classes range from EXC1 to EXC4 and exhibit increasing levels of requirements. Each EXC specifies the expected level of requirements concerning quality, execution, and control, both within the workshop and on-site. Furthermore, EN 1090-2 (1) references ISO 5817 (2) for the quality levels of welds associated with the execution classes. Currently, prEN 1993-1-8 (3) imposes EXC2 for all welded connections, corresponding to quality level C.

The background justification for adopting a quality level C in prEN 1993-1-8 (3) remains somewhat limited. Nonetheless, a quality level D is widely implemented in practical applications, particularly in the construction of small steel structures. Limited research has been conducted to establish a clear link between weld imperfections and their effects on the static resistance of welds. Sugitani and Mochizuki (5) demonstrated that increasing the root gap in a fillet weld resulted in greater penetration

depth, subsequently enhancing static strength. They highlighted the importance of penetration depth, showing that a fillet weld with lower penetration and larger throat size exhibited lower resistance compared to one with higher penetration and smaller throat size. Sedmak et al. (6) studied experimentally the behaviour of butt-welded connection with multiple imperfections, including undercut, incomplete root penetration, misalignment, sagging, and excess weld metal. Notably, misalignment significantly affected the weld resistance by shifting stress concentration from high-strength weld metal to low-strength base metal. Finally, Voelkel et al. (7) observed that, the axial misalignment quality levels covered in ISO 5817 (2) did not influence the load-bearing capacity of butt-weld connections. However, misalignments affected the failure location.

The lack of research establishing a link between the weld imperfections and their static resistance has motivated the authors to initiate experimental tests. The experimental campaign aims to investigate imperfections that have not been studied such weld asymmetry and porosities, but also to complete existing experimental tests (5, 7) regarding root gap and axial misalignment. The quality level limitations of these imperfections according to ISO 5817 (2) are provided in *Table 1* for plate thicker than 3mm.

Table 1 : Imperfection limits according to quality levels outlined in ISO 5817 (2)

Reference to ISO 6520-1 (4)	Imperfection designation	Remarks	Limits for imperfections for quality level		
			D	C	B
512	Excessive asymmetry of fillet weld		$h \leq 0,2a_A + 2mm$	$h \leq 0,15a_A + 2mm$	$h \leq 0,15a_A + 1,5mm$
2012	Uniformly distributed porosity	A_1 is the maximum dimension of the area of the imperfections related to the projected area	For single layer: $A_1 \leq 2,5\%$	For single layer: $A_1 \leq 1,5\%$	For single layer: $A_1 \leq 1\%$
			For multi-layer: $A_1 \leq 5\%$	For multi-layer: $A_1 \leq 3\%$	For multi-layer: $A_1 \leq 2\%$
		A_2 is the maximum dimension of the cross-sectional area of the imperfections related to the fracture area	$A_2 \leq 2,5\%$	$A_2 \leq 1,5\%$	$A_2 \leq 1\%$
	Maximum diameter "d" for a single pore	$d \leq 0,4a$ but max. 5mm	$d \leq 0,3a$ but max. 4mm	$d \leq 0,2a$ but max. 3mm	
617	Incorrect root gap for fillet welds		$g \leq 0,3a + 1mm$ but max. 4mm	$g \leq 0,2a + 0,5mm$ but max. 4mm	$g \leq 0,1a + 0,5mm$ but max. 4mm
5071	Linear misalignment between plates		$m \leq 0,25t$ but max. 5mm	$m \leq 0,15t$ but max. 4mm	$m \leq 0,1t$ but max. 3mm

Figure 2: Definition of throat thickness and gap height

3 NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING

After the fabrication of all specimens and before destructive static tests, non-destructive testing (NDT) has been performed to characterize and quantify weld imperfections, providing valuable insights into their distribution along the weld. *Figure 3* illustrates the three NDT methods used in this experimental campaign. Visual testing (VT) was meticulously conducted to ensure a comprehensive examination of the weld surface integrity. A multi-purpose gauge was utilized to measure key parameters, encompassing the weld throat thickness, leg length of fillet weld, and the depth of undercuts. Taking precision to the next level, 3D scanning using GO!SCAN SPARK was incorporated into the testing protocol, offering detailed information about linear and angular misalignments. In addition to visual testing and 3D scanning, ultrasonic testing (UT) with phased array technology was deployed to inspect the internal structure of the weld. This method provided crucial information about the presence of internal imperfections such as inclusions and porosities. “Institut de Soudure” conducted both ultrasonic testing and 3D scanning. The combined application of NDT methods formed a robust framework for evaluating the quality level of the welded specimens before static tests.

Figure 3: Non-destructive testing methods

Table 3 shows the measured throat thickness of all the tested specimens, along with the corresponding quality level regarding the excessive asymmetry of each fillet weld. It is noteworthy that specimens labelled as “Ti” were supposed to have a weld throat thickness of 10 mm. However, due to a misunderstanding, welders executed a 5 mm throat thickness.

The test specimens revealed a notable disparity in the quality levels of fillet welds concerning the excessive asymmetry. While certain welds met the stringent criteria of quality level B, others did not meet the D threshold. Notably, some specimens displayed diverse quality levels across their four fillet welds, exemplified by specimen “M3”. This variability underscores the sensitivity of fillet welds to

imperfections, emphasizing the need for precise execution and highlighting potential challenges in achieving uniform quality across all tested specimens.

Table 3 : Weld throat thicknesses

Test specimen	Weld throat thickness			
	a_{ur} [mm]	a_{ul} [mm]	a_{lr} [mm]	a_{ll} [mm]
T1	5.4	6.5	5.5	4.9
T2	5.0	5.8	6.0	4.9
T3	4.5	6.9	4.3	4.9
P1	10.3	9.8	12.5	10.3
P2	10.3	11.1	11.6	10.6
P3	9.8	12.2	11.9	12.0
PM1	11.0	13.0	10.6	11.2
PM2	11.3	10.7	11.1	11.4
PM3	11.3	10.1	10.2	11.0
G1	10.0	9.5	8.6	10.2
G2	9.3	9.9	8.8	10.2
G3	9.5	9.9	8.7	9.9
G4	9.6	10	11.7	10.8
G5	10.3	11.1	11.6	10.4
G6	10.4	10.7	11.5	10.1
GM1	10.3	10.6	10.9	11.3
GM2	10.5	10.5	9.9	11.2
GM3	10.9	10.2	10.1	11.9
M1	9.7	9.9	10.1	11
M2	10.5	10.4	10.8	11.2
M3	10.3	9.9	10.4	10.6

	Quality level B for excessive asymmetry of fillet weld
	Quality level C for excessive asymmetry of fillet weld
	Quality level D for excessive asymmetry of fillet weld
	Quality level higher than D for excessive asymmetry of fillet weld

Table 4 offers a comprehensive overview of the quality levels associated with different imperfections such as porosities, root gap, and misalignment. Concerning porosities within a weld, the phased array ultrasonic testing technique successfully detected the presence of pores but could not quantify them in terms of percentage area, as required by ISO 5817 (2). The ultrasonic testing technique provided results based on “acceptance levels”, according to ISO 19285 (10) recommendations. Notably, acceptance level 3 corresponds to quality levels C and D, while acceptance level 2 corresponds to quality level B. It is important to highlight that distinguishing between quality levels D and C for porosities was not possible.

During the fabrication of the specimens, welders were instructed to avoid angular misalignments. However, as evidenced in Table 4, angular misalignment was more pronounced in the “Ti” specimens and those featuring a root gap (specimens “Gi” and “GMi”). It is noteworthy that ISO 5817 (2) does not prescribe specific limits for angular misalignment within its imperfection criteria, making it challenging to classify into defined quality levels. Nevertheless, Annex B of ISO 5817 (2) introduces additional criteria for welds subject to fatigue, addressing the consideration of angular misalignment in such cases.

Table 4 : Quality levels of imperfections present of tested specimens

Test specimen	Quality level of porosity	Incorrect root gap “g” [mm]	Quality level	Linear misalignment “m” [mm]	Quality level	Angular misalignment [°]
T1	B	0.0	B	0.7	B	1.1
T2	B	0.0	B	1.0	B	1.6
T3	B	0.0	B	0.8	B	1.0
P1	> D	0.0	B	1.1	B	0.3
P2	> D	0.0	B	2.2	C	0.3
P3	> D	0.0	B	1.2	B	0.2
PM1	> D	0.0	B	4.5	D	0.2
PM2	> D	0.0	B	4.6	D	0.8
PM3	> D	0.0	B	4.8	D	0.1
G1	B	1.9	C	3.0	C	1.4
G2	B	1.7	C	2.7	C	1.4
G3	B	1.8	C	1.2	B	1.3
G4	B	2.6	C	1.5	B	1.1
G5	B	2.8	D	1.5	B	1.2
G6	B	3.0	D	1.2	B	1.4
GM1	B	1.4	B	4.6	D	0.8
GM2	B	1.1	B	4.0	D	0.6
GM3	B	2.3	C	3.9	D	0.9
M1	B	0.0	B	4.4	D	1.0
M2	B	0.0	B	4.4	D	0.7
M3	B	0.0	B	4.0	D	1.0

4 STATIC TEST RESULTS

The ultimate resistance, $N_{u,exp}$, and failure modes of specimens tested under static loading are presented in *Table 5*. In addition, the analytical resistance calculated according to the directional method of prEN 1993-1-8 (3) without partial factor is added. The corresponding ultimate resistance was determined using *Eq. (1)*.

$$N_r = \frac{f_u a L_w}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (1)$$

With:

a : Average throat thickness of side that failed during testing, extracted from *Table 3*

L_w : Total weld length

f_u : Ultimate tensile strength extracted from the material certificate as shown in *Table 2*

To enhance accuracy, a tensile test on the filler metal will be performed in the future. The failure of all specimens except GM2 developed in the weld metal. For this latter, the failure appeared in the base metal.

Table 5 : Summary of test results

Specimen	Failure location	$N_{u,exp}$ [kN]	$N_{u,ana}$ [kN]	Force ratio “R”
				$R = \frac{N_{u,exp}}{N_{u,ana}}$
T1	Weld metal	402.3	285.9	1.41
T2	Weld metal	409.5	266.2	1.54
T3	Weld metal	418.9	226.8	1.85
P1	Weld metal	448.3	493.0	0.91
P2	Weld metal	464.3	527.5	0.88
P3	Weld metal	517.8	542.3	0.95
PM1	Weld metal	531.2	591.6	0.90
PM2	Weld metal	585.7	542.3	1.08
PM3	Weld metal	623.2	527.5	1.18
G1	Weld metal	656.2	483.1	1.36
G2	Weld metal	686.4	473.3	1.45
G3	Weld metal	694.4	478.2	1.45
G4	Weld metal	622.9	557.1	1.12
G5	Weld metal	634.4	542.3	1.17
G6	Weld metal	692.7	532.4	1.30
GM1	Weld metal	727.6	512.7	1.42
GM2	Base metal	736.4	-	-
GM3	Weld metal	711.1	517.6	1.37
M1	Weld metal	652.9	483.1	1.35
M2	Weld metal	679.8	512.7	1.33
M3	Weld metal	706.7	497.9	1.42

Specimens T1, T2, and T3 exhibit no imperfections and thus represent the reference value for joint strength. These specimens display a high force ratio ranging between 1.41 and 1.85. A higher ratio value indicates a greater disparity between the calculated force $N_{u,ana}$ and the experimental force $N_{u,exp}$. It was expected that the directional method would yield a lower strength value compared to the experimental results. However, a smaller ratio indicates that the two force values are closer, showing that the current imperfections have a significant effect on the experimental force $N_{u,exp}$, reducing it to align with the calculated one $N_{u,ana}$.

Test specimens “Pi” and “PMi” exhibit severe porosity, surpassing the limits defined for quality level D in both welds “a_{ur}” and “a_{ul}”, as illustrated in *Figure 4*. Additionally, welds “a_{ur}” and “a_{ul}” are characterized by an excessive asymmetry of fillet welds that exceeds the specified limits for quality level D. However, a notable distinction arises in the linear misalignment, graded at quality level B in specimens P1 and P3, quality level C in P2 and quality level D in specimens PM1, PM2 and PM3.

Figure 4 : Test specimens “Pi” and “PMi”

It is worth highlighting the significant impact of porosity on weld resistance, as evidenced by a substantial decreased in the force ratio by 0.95 in specimen P3 and 1.08 in specimen PM2. However, the influence of linear misalignment on the maximum force $N_{u,exp}$ was not identifiable, as the specimens with no misalignment “Pi” showed almost the same results as the one with misalignment “PMi” (0.91 for specimen P1 vs. 0.90 for specimen PM1).

Joints “Gi” and “GMi” displayed varying dimensions of incorrect root gaps as seen in *Figure 5*, sometimes accompanied by other imperfections. Among the test specimens, G1, G2, and G3 exhibited a root gap quality level C, with linear misalignment quality level C for specimens G1 and G2 and quality level B for specimen G3. The force ratio of these three specimens ranged from 1.36 to 1.45, which is smaller than the average ratio of the “T” specimens (1.60). It is noteworthy, that the failure location occurred on the weld side with no root gap (welds “a_{ur}” and “a_{ul}”), leaving the side that presents a root gap unfailed. Therefore, a root gap quality level C did not negatively affect the weld resistance.

Figure 5 : Specimens presenting different root gap height and linear misalignment

A significant difference emerged in the test results of specimen G4, G5 and G6, where the failure location occurred on the side of the root gap. Specimen G5 and G6 had a root gap quality level D, while speciemn G4 maintain a quality level C. Despite specimens with a root gap quality level D exhibiting higher penetration than that of root gap C, the force ratio showed a lower value. The ratio in these specimens decreased to range from 1.12 to 1.30. When investigating the reason for this decrease in weld resistance, it was noteworthy that specimens G4, G5, and G6 exhibited an additional lack of root fusion as seen in *Figure 6*. It is worth noting that increasing the gap height and root penetration has increased the sensitivity to lack of root fusion, emphasizing the importance of correct base metal preparation to ensure full penetration.

Figure 6 : Specimens “Gi” fractures

Specimens GM1, GM2 and GM3 possess all a linear misalignment quality level D. However, specimen GM3 stands out by additionally exhibiting a root gap of quality level C. Remarkably, specimen GM2 distinguishes itself as the only specimen to experience failure in the base metal. Conversely, specimen GM3 failed from the side of the root gap, resulting in a force ratio lower than that of specimen GM1 (1.37 vs. 1.42). The transition from quality level C to D in misalignment did not demonstrated a noticeable impact, as specimen GM3, with a force ratio of 1.37, showed a similar

resistance to specimens G1 and G2, with force ratios of 1.36 and 1.45 respectively. This suggests that there is no discernible impact on weld resistance when transitioning from quality level C to D in misalignment.

Figure 7 : Specimen “Mi” with linear misalignment

For further insights of linear misalignment, specimens M1, M2 and M3 were fabricated with a quality level D for misalignment, coupled with a quality level higher than D of excess asymmetry in fillet welds, as depicted in *Figure 7*. Despite exhibiting lower force ratios compared to the “Ti” specimens, they demonstrated ratios comparable to those of specimens with a linear misalignment quality level C (G1 and G2). This observation supports the conclusion that there is no significant difference in resistance between quality levels D and C for misalignment. However, regarding fillet weld asymmetry, it became evident that this imperfection was unintentionally present alongside porosities and the linear misalignment. Its impact on the weld resistance is evident, as its coexistence with linear misalignment, decreased the force ratio to 1.35 (specimen M1) compared to the the average ratio of the “Ti” specimens (1.60).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This research investigates the relationship between the quality levels of weld imperfections and their static resistance in load-carrying cruciform joints. The study conducted a comprehensive experimental campaign to analyse various imperfections, including porosity, incorrect root gap, linear misalignment, and excessive asymmetry of fillet welds. Non-destructive test were meticulously employed to measure and locate imperfections, in order to determine their appropriate quality level according to ISO 5817 (2). The study provides insights into the nuanced effects of different imperfections on weld resistance, leading to the following conclusions:

- The distinction between quality levels C and D, as outlined in ISO 5817 (2), presents a practical challenge. ISO 5817 (2) relies on the appropriate non-destructive testing standard to establish these quality levels. For example, when using ultrasonic testing, ISO 19285 (10) is the reference standard. However, it does not precisely quantify the porosity area or differentiate between quality levels C and D. Consequently, the requirement for achieving quality level C in prEN 1993-1-8 (3) requires re-evaluation due to the impracticality of distinguishing between the two levels in practice.
- Among all the imperfections studied, weld porosities exert the most significant effect on weld resistance. For instance, specimen P2 exhibits a force ratio of 0.88, which is significantly lower than the 1.54 observed for specimen type T2. In contrast, linear misalignment has the least pronounced effect on weld resistance, as evidenced by a force ratio of 1.35 for specimen M1. A comparison of specimens with varying quality levels of misalignment shows that transitioning from quality level C to D has no significant impact on weld resistance.
- Increasing the height of the root gap enhances penetration depth. However, inadequate accessibility to the weld root during welding results in a lack of root fusion, ultimately

weakening the weld. A comparison of specimens with different quality levels of the root gap reveals that those with a quality level C have higher weld resistance than those with a quality level D.

- Certain imperfections often coexist with others. Notably, a root gap can lead to a lack of root fusion, which in turn reduces weld strength. Additionally, linear misalignment and porosities may be accompanied by excessive asymmetry in fillet welds. It is important to note that angular misalignment is prevalent in all specimens, although ISO 5817 (2) does not specify a limitation for this imperfection.

The presented research findings raise concerns about the necessity of quality level C adopted in prEN 1993-1-8 (3). The outcome of the 21 tested specimens emphasizes the interest for a thorough re-evaluation of the quality level C. Additional experimental tests are being prepared to expand the scope of the study to include other imperfections, such as undercuts, end crater pipes, and lack of penetration. These tests will also include a comprehensive analysis of various joint geometries and dimensions.

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